

POLYPHEM
THE FUTURE OF SMALL-SCALE CSP PLANTS

POLYPHEM

Small-Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle

D2.4 PLC Controller

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SUMMARY	<p>This document is the deliverable D2.4 of the project POLYPHEM. It is planned in the framework of the Work Package WP2. The document describes the prototype of Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) as it was designed to meet the technical requirements of the POLYPHEM plant. The PLC relies on the technology developed by Siemens. This system can host 64 local I/O devices associated to the components distributed in the plant: gas-turbine, combustor, lubrication unit, generators, bottom cycle... A network Profinet is implemented to communicate with the components from/to the control room.</p> <p>The content of this deliverable fully complies with the Grant Agreement number 764048 signed between the beneficiaries and the European Commission. It also complies with the project Consortium Agreement signed by the beneficiaries. This deliverable cannot replace the role neither of the Grant Agreement nor of the Consortium Agreement, which are evidence for the project.]</p>
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Background: about the POLYPHEM project

FULL TITLE	SMALL-SCALE SOLAR THERMAL COMBINED-CYCLE
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The POLYPHEM project is a research and innovation action funded by the European Union's H2020 program. It is implemented by a European consortium of 4 research centres and 5 industrial partners. The aim is to increase the flexibility and improve the performance of small solar tower power plants. The concept of POLYPHEM consists in implementing a combined cycle formed by a solarized micro gas-turbine and a Rankine organic cycle machine, with an integrated thermal storage device between the two cycles. The need for cooling is minimal.

Developed from a patented technology by CNRS and CEA, the pressurized air solar receiver is integrated in the micro-turbine cycle. The thermal efficiency targeted for the receiver is 80% with a cost of 400 €/kW. The innovative thermal storage uses a thermal oil and a single thermocline tank with a technical concrete filler material.

The main expected impact of this project is to enhance the competitiveness of low-carbon energy production systems through the technology developed. The expected progress is a better fitting of electricity generation to variable local needs, an overall conversion efficiency of solar energy into electricity of 18% for an investment cost of less than 5 €/W and a low environmental impact. By 2030, the cost of electricity production targeted by the POLYPHEM technology is 165 €/MWh for an annual direct normal irradiation of 2600 kWh/m²/year (North Africa and Middle East) and 209 €/MWh under 2050 kWh/m²/year (Southern Europe). In addition to decentralized power generation, other applications are considered for the deployment of this technology used in poly-generation: industrial heat production, solar heating and cooling, desalination of seawater or brackish water.

A prototype plant of 60 kW_{el} with a thermal storage of 1300 kWh is designed, built and installed on the site of the experimental solar tower of Themis in Targasonne (France). The objective of the project is to validate the technical choices under test conditions representative of actual operating conditions.

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*Table of content***1. Demonstrator for PLC Controller.** _____ **5***List of Acronyms and Abbreviations*

Acronym/abbreviation	Meaning/full text
AALB	Aalborg CSP
ARRA	Arraela S.L.
CA	Consortium Agreement
CEA	Commissariat à l’Energie Atomique
CIEMAT	Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas, Medioambientales y Tecnologicas
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
CO	Confidential
CPU	Central Processing Unit
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
EURO	Euronovia
FISE	Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems, ISE
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
I/O	Input/Output
M	Month
MRP	Media Redundancy Protocol
MS	Milestone
ORC	Orcan Energy GmbH or Organic Rankine Cycle
PU	Public
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
WP	Work Package

1. DEMONSTRATOR FOR POLYPHEM PLC CONTROLLER.

The PLC controller serves as an overall control system for the entire power plant. It is the interface between sensors that measure physical values and actuators for valves or electric machines (pumps, frequency converter).

For Polyphem project a SIEMENS PLC (*Simatic S7-1500 series*, see Table 1) has been chosen, which enables fail-safe-automation (SIL 3 classification).

Technical Specification	
Work Memory for SPS program	6 Mbyte
Work Memory for SPS data	20 Mbyte
Work Memory for CPU function library of CPU Runtime (C/C++ functions)	50 Mbyte
Working memory for additional functions	1 Gbyte
CPU processing times	
for bit operations, typ.	1 ns
for word operations, typ.	2 ns
for fixed point arithmetic, typ.	2 ns
for floating point arithmetic, typ.	6 ns
Number of program blocks	12000
Number of IO modules	16384
Number of distributed IO systems	64
Number of <i>Profinet</i> Interfaces	3
Number of <i>Profibus</i> Interfaces	1

Table 1: SIEMENS 1518F-4PN/DP MFP main specification parameters

For the selected PLC system different types of interconnection modules (I/O modules) or periphery modules are available. The interconnection modules are used with interface modules to enable a decentralized structure of I/O modules that are connected via a single fieldbus wire (*also known as decentralized periphery*). The used fieldbus is *Profinet*. Furthermore, the frequency converter for the power-block communicates with this fieldbus. The connection wire can be electric or optical type (for galvanic decoupling and high distance communication).

The topology of the communication system with the decentralized periphery, the CPU, the HMI and the frequency converter are shown in Figure 1. I/O modules are placed in in the machine room (top of the tower) for monitoring and controlling the turbine, the lubrication system and the gas-combustor. At the bottom of the tower a decentralized periphery for monitoring and controlling the bottom cycle is placed.

Figure 1: Polyphem control system topology (respecting various hardware locations)

The decentralized peripheral packages are connected with the frequency converter by the bus system *Profinet* in MRP configuration. This configuration is a redundant ring topology.

The PLC and the HMI (human machine interface) are installed in a control room that is placed outside the tower.

The hardware described above is shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3.

Figure 2: periphery modules for decentralized I/O connection (SIEMENS ET200SP with power supply)

Figure 3: SIEMENS 1518F-4PN/DP MFP with power supply